

The Use of Graph Neural Networks for Clustering in Road Safety Analysis

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Introduction

➤ Road crashes claim **1.3 million lives annually**, the leading cause of death for those **under 29** and among the top 10 globally.

➤ IVORY framework.

- [European Union's Horizon Europe](#) research and innovation programme Marie Skłodowska-Curie Industrial Doctorates (grant No 101119590).
- It develops fair and explainable **Artificial Intelligence (AI)** to analyze driver behavior, predict crashes, and enhance road safety while sharing knowledge.
- DC9 focuses on creating an AI framework to analyze **road safety KPIs**, predicts crashes, and evaluates the **scalability of models** primarily across spatial.

➤ Traditional crash prediction relies on econometrics; now enhanced by **Machine Learning (ML)** & **Deep Learning (DL)**, with **Graph Neural Networks (GNNs)** extend DL to graph-structured data.

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OSeven Telematics Data

- OSeven Telematics provided **telematics data** collected via smartphone hardware sensors to monitor driver behavior.
- All trips are anonymized and compliant with Greek and European personal **data protection** regulations (GDPR).
- Raw data are processed by **proprietary machine learning** algorithms. Reliability is validated against OBD data, on-road tests, simulators, and literature benchmarks.
- Selected **features**: geographic coordinates, smoothed speed, and binary flags for speeding, mobile usage, harsh acceleration, and harsh braking.

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OpenStreetMap

OpenStreetMap

- A free, editable **global map** created by volunteers and released under an open-content license.
- The previous dataset defines a coordinate **bounding box** used to extract a structured **graph** from OpenStreetMap via the **OSMnx** Python library.
 - Study area: urban road network in Athens, Greece.
- From the extracted graph, **node** and **edge** features were saved into two separate datasets.
 - These datasets were cleaned and preprocessed by removing irrelevant columns and ensuring data quality (e.g., handling duplicates and missing values).

Telematics Aggregation

- Telematics features were aggregated to OSM nodes using summation or averaging within a **50-meter buffer**.
- Each raw telematics point was matched to its **closest edge**, and features were aggregated per edge similarly to the node-level process.
- The number of trips was calculated for each node and edge as **exposure metric** and the **street_count** attribute from OSM was added.
- Not all nodes/edges contain telematics data—**coverage** depends on trip paths.

Features	Description
Street_Count	Number of streets connected to the intersection
SmoothenedSpeed	Average speed of vehicles near the node
SpeedingFlag	Count of speeding events near the node
Mobile_usage	Number of instances of phone usage near the node
Harsh_acc	Number of harsh acceleration events near the node
Harsh_brk	Number of harsh braking events near the node
Trips_count	Number of trips recorded near the node

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Clustering with K-means

- Given a dataset of points $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$, K-Means aims to **partition** them into K , clusters $\{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_k\}$, by minimizing the total **within-cluster sum of squared distances**:

$$\arg \min_C \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{x_i \in C_k} \|x_i - \mu_k\|^2$$

Where μ_k is the centroid (mean) of cluster C_k , and $\|x_i - \mu_k\|^2$ is the squared Euclidean distance.

- K-Means: **efficient** and **widely used**.

- Linear time complexity, fast convergence, low memory use.
- Easy to implement and interpret, using clear centroids and simple assignments.
- It is sensitive to initial centroids (can converge to local minima).

Choosing the Optimal Number of Clusters (K)

➤ Elbow Method

- Plots Within-Cluster Sum of Squares (WCSS) against K to identify the "elbow point" where adding more clusters no longer significantly reduces WCSS.
- This point indicates a good trade-off between model complexity and explained variance.

➤ Silhouette Score

- It measures how well a data point fits within its own cluster compared to other clusters.

Average silhouette score quantifies overall cluster cohesion and separation.

Artificial Neural Networks

- Inspiration: Modeled after the structure of the human brain, consisting of layers of **interconnected neurons**.
- **Structure:**
 - Input layer receives **raw data**.
 - This data pass through one or multiple **hidden layers** that transform the input into data that is valuable for the output layer.
 - The output layer produces the **predicted result** based on the transformed information from the hidden layers.
- **Key Concepts:**
 - Activation functions introduce non-linearity.
 - Backpropagation updates parameters to minimize loss.
 - Loss Function guides learning, depending on the task.

Introduction to GNNs

- GNNs are specialized artificial neural networks that are designed for tasks whose **inputs are graphs**.
- GNNs can be used to learn **node embeddings**: compact **vector representations** capturing each node's **structural role, neighborhood context, and features**.
- They encode graph-structured data by leveraging **topological relationships** rather than flattening the graph into vectors.
- Advancements include **Graph Convolutional Networks** (GCN) using convolution operations, and **Graph Attention Networks** (GAT) applying attention mechanisms.

Attention-Based GNNs

- The GAT model is a novel neural network architecture **leveraging attention** mechanisms.
- It is a **specialized form of GCN** that improves how neighbor information is aggregated by learning attention weights dynamically.
- A simple neural network with two GAT layers has been defined.
 - Leverages **attention coefficients** (α_{ij}) to weigh neighbors differently and to incorporate both **edge features** and **neighboring nodes**.
 - Using a **multi-head attention** (α_{ij}^k) to stabilize training, improve accuracy and simplify output by averaging heads.

$$\mathbf{h}'_i = \sigma \left(\frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{j \in N_i \cup \{i\}} \alpha_{ij}^k \mathbf{W}^k \mathbf{h}_j \right)$$

Attention for Node Embeddings

- The **attention coefficients** quantify how much influence node j should have when updating **node i 's embedding**.
 - A node is not equally influenced by all its neighbors, the GAT learns which surrounding nodes matter more prioritizing those that provide more meaningful context through attention.
- **Edge Features Matter**
 - If you include edge features, the model learns attention based on **how nodes are connected, not just if they are connected**.
- The attention coefficient α_{ij} can be interpreted as a **learned weight of relevance**:
 - **High** α_{ij} → Neighbor j is highly relevant for understanding node i 's role in the network.
 - **Low** α_{ij} → Neighbor j is less informative for understanding node i 's role in the network.
- **Localized understanding** of how risk or driver patterns propagate across a road network.

$$\alpha_{ij} = \frac{e^{(\text{LeakyReLU}(\mathbf{a}_s^T \boldsymbol{\theta}_s \mathbf{x}_i + \mathbf{a}_t^T \boldsymbol{\theta}_t \mathbf{x}_j + \mathbf{a}_e^T \boldsymbol{\theta}_e \mathbf{e}_{i,j}))}}{\sum_{k \in N_i \cup i} e^{(\text{LeakyReLU}(\mathbf{a}_s^T \boldsymbol{\theta}_s \mathbf{x}_i + \mathbf{a}_t^T \boldsymbol{\theta}_t \mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{a}_e^T \boldsymbol{\theta}_e \mathbf{e}_{i,k}))}}$$

Self-Supervised Training

- Inspired by **contrastive learning** frameworks.
 - For each node, compute **cosine similarity** with neighbors and random non-neighbors.
 - Scale similarities with **temperature** and apply **exponential function** $\rightarrow e^{S_{i,j}^+}$
 - **Sum** values over neighbors and non-neighbors separately.
 - Compute **ratio** of neighbor sum to total sum, then apply **logarithm**.
 - Final loss is **averaged over all nodes**, optimizing to learn embeddings that reflect **shared characteristics and connectivity**.
 - Training over **10 epochs** using subgraphs sampled by PyG NeighborLoader.
 - Optimization done with **Adam optimizer**.

$$\mathcal{L}_i = -\log \left(\frac{\sum_{j \in P_i} e^{S_{i,j}^+}}{\sum_{j \in P_i} e^{S_{i,j}^+} + \sum_{j \in N_i} e^{S_{i,j}^-}} \right)$$

Clustering on Raw Features

➤ Clustering on **Raw Features**:

- No clear elbow in the inertia curve → suggests gradual improvement **without a sharp optimal K**.
- K-Means clustering on raw features yielded a highest **silhouette** score of 0.58 for $K = 2$ → **modest separation** between the two clusters.
- **Inertia** of 145909, a 20% reduction from $K=1$ (inertia of 192556).

Embeddings

- At this stage, the **GAT model** was used to involve the features of the edges connected to each node, besides the road network topology.
- The **edge features** mirror those of the nodes, excluding `street_count` and supplemented by **four additional features**:
 - Edge **length**.
 - Two **binary features** were derived via one-hot encoding from a three-category variable indicating **road type** (service, urban, rural).
 - A **binary oneway column** shows if vehicles can go in only one direction or in both directions.

Clustering on Embeddings

➤ Clustering on **Embeddings**:

- No clear elbow in the inertia curve → suggests gradual improvement **without a sharp optimal K**.
- K-Means applied to GNN-generated embeddings showed a **silhouette** score of 0.73 for K=2 → **strong separation** between the two clusters.
- **Inertia** of 2530, a 28% reduction from K=1 (inertia of 3501).
- GNN has captured **latent network structure** that may not be visible in raw features.

Clustering Comparison

- The groups identified by both clustering methods exhibit similar characteristics upon comparison.
- Green nodes represent **safer behaviors**, while red nodes are associated with **less safe events** and **more trips**.
- However, the clustering based on the embeddings tends to **polarize** the nodes, **shrinking** the less safe cluster while **expanding** the other one.

Clustering type	Safer nodes	Riskier nodes
Simple Clustering	24776	2732
Embeddings Clustering	26587	921

Assessing Clustering Results

➤ Each metric captures a different aspect of clustering quality:

- **WCSS**

Measures intra-cluster compactness.

❖ *Lower values suggest tighter, more cohesive clusters.*

- **Silhouette**

Evaluates how similar a point is to its own cluster vs others.

❖ *Higher values indicate well-separated, dense clusters.*

- **Davies-Bouldin Index (DBI)**

Compares intra-cluster and inter-cluster distances.

❖ *Lower values reflect tighter and better separated clusters.*

- **Calinski-Harabasz Index (CHI)**

Assesses cluster dispersion relative to the overall data spread.

❖ *Higher scores indicate well-separated, distinct clusters.*

Index	Simple Clustering value	Embeddings Clustering value
WCSS	145909	2530
Silhouette	0.58	0.73
DBI	1.41	0.98
CHI	8794	10551

$$DBI = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k \max_{i \neq j} \left(\frac{S_i + S_j}{M_{ij}} \right)$$

$$CHI = \frac{Tr(B_k)}{Tr(W_k)} \frac{n - k}{n - 1}$$

Overview of the Identified Groups

	Street_Count	Smoothened Speed	SpeedingFlag	Mobile_usage	Harsh_acc	Harsh_brk	Trips_count
Risky Cluster	3.15	47.93	19.78	6.42	0.38	0.33	92.2
Safer Cluster	3.34	28.55	0.92	2.27	0.09	0.08	20.24

- Mapped **embedding cluster labels to raw data** and averaged features per cluster to interpret differences.
 - Within the **risky group** of nodes, drivers tend to travel at higher speeds, with **SpeedingFlag** triggered on average 20 times more often.
 - There is also a higher prevalence of **phone usage** and **harsh driving events**.
 - These nodes are more heavily trafficked, as indicated by a greater **number of trips**.
 - In contrast, the **safer group** is characterized by lower traffic volumes and generally **better driving behavior**, including reduced speeds and fewer risky events.

Discussion

➤ Numerical and Conceptual Reflections

- The **clear quantitative separation** between groups validates the use of embedding-based clustering for identifying meaningful clusters. The magnitude of difference in key indicators (e.g., 20× speeding events) supports the **practical relevance of the classification**.
- The results align with known **road safety principles**: higher speeds and distracted driving increase risk.

➤ Methodology Suitability

- Clustering telematics and geometric features effectively identifies **distinct areas within a road network**.
- Reliance on aggregate averages may mask **temporal variations**.
- Integrating cluster labels with raw features and averaging values per cluster bridges the gap between **complex representation learning** and **real-world feature insights**, improving explainability.

Potential applications

- The work provides actionable insights, informing on where to focus safety efforts and resources, aiming to improve overall **traffic management** and **public safety**.
 - Risky cluster areas can be targeted for interventions, such as **infrastructure improvements**, awareness **campaigns**, or **enforcement measures**, to enhance road safety.
 - Insurers can use this clustering to define **risk profiles** by identifying patterns of risky or safe driving behavior.
 - Drivers in high-risk clusters may face **higher premiums**, while those in safer clusters could benefit from **discounts**.
 - This also enables insurers to offer more accurate, **location-based pricing** and **targeted advice**.

Conclusions

- Graph-based representations enhance understanding of **complex road safety data**.
- By incorporating node features, topology, and edge attributes **clustering performance** are improved.
- K-Means used as baseline for efficiency; **alternative clustering** methods could be explored.
- Future directions include testing **different GNN architectures** and **loss functions**.
- Adding **traffic** and **temporal features** may increase real-world applicability and impact.

Thank you for the attention

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